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IN SILICO APPROACH TO IDENTIFY PUTATIVE DRUGS FROM NATURAL PRODUCTS FOR HUMAN PAPILOMAVIRUS (HPV) WHICH CAUSE CERVICAL CANCER

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ABSTRACT:

Cervical cancer is a malignant neoplasm of the cervix uteri that starts in the cervix and is the second most common type of cancer in women worldwide. Human papillomavirus (HPV) is the primary causal agent of cervical cancer. Among high-risk strains, HPV 16 is the most closely associated with cervical carcinoma. The two early proteins of HPV 16, E6 and E7, play a significant role in tumor formation. The proteins E6 and E7 are involved in cellular transformation. The transforming properties of E6 and E7 proteins result, in part, from their ability to modulate many host proteins that regulate cell growth and differentiation. The present study was carried out to identify novel putative drugs, which bind with both E6 and E7 proteins of HPV which causes the cervical cancer. The drug targets E6 and E7 were carefully chosen from literature and the 3D structure was modeled by *ab initio* method. The natural product library was constructed from various databases and literature to find the most suitable putative drug. All the ligands were docked using Molegro Virtual Docker and the lead molecules were investigated for ADME and toxicity.

KEY WORDS: Human papillomavirus (HPV), Molegro Virtual Docker (MVD),

Modeling, Docking, ADMET, Drug targets.

INTRODUCTION:

Cervical cancer is malignant carcinoma of the cervix region of the lower part of the uterus that opens at the top of the vagina. It is the second most common type of cancer occurs in women worldwide and a major cause of mortality predominantly in developing countries where it accounts for 15% of all new female cancers, with an estimated 470,000 new cases and 230,000 deaths (Beaudenon & Huibregtse, 2008; Quinn *et. al.*, 2006). Human papillomavirus (HPV) as the primary causative agent in development of cervical carcinoma. These HPV types have therefore appeared as one of the most significant identified risk factors for widespread human cancers. Till now there have been more than 200 types of HPVs are identified. Nearly 99% of cervical cancers contain HPV DNA of the high-risk types. Among high-risk strains, HPV 16 and 18 are those most closely associated with cervical carcinoma that are found in >50% and 20% of squamous cell carcinomas, respectively (Walboomers *et. al.*, 1999).

The two early proteins of HPV 16, E6 and E7, play a significant role in tumor formation. E6 and E7 proteins are involved in cellular transformation. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies show that the functions of high-risk E6 and E7, of being necessary for the induction and maintenance of the transformed phenotype of cervical cancer cells by hijacking cellular pathways. The transforming properties of E6 and E7 proteins result, in part, from their ability to modulate many host proteins that regulate cell growth and differentiation (Burk, Chen, & Van Doorslaer, 2009; Duffy, Phillips, & Klingelutz, 2003; Munger & Phelps, 1993).

The E6 and E7 proteins of HPV16 and HPV18 are associated with cervical cancer. The most characteristic feature of all HPV E6 proteins is the presence of four Cys-X-X-Cys motifs which permit the formation of two zinc fingers. E6 binds to cellular proteins, in particular E6AP and E6BP, thereby modulating normal cellular processes. The E6-E6AP complex can bind *in vitro* to p53 or to E6BP. HPV E6 has been shown to be capable of interfering with the cellular controls of DNA replication, through Mcm7 (Kuhne & Banks, 1998); chromosomal structure, through telomerase (Klingelutz, Foster, & McDougall, 1996); cytoskeletal structure, through paxillin (Tong & Howley, 1997); cell polarity, through DLG; signal transduction, through E6TP1, paxillin, c-Myc and E6BP (Chen, Reid, Band, & Androphy, 1995); differentiation, through E6BP and c-Myc; and apoptosis, through Bak and c-Myc (Vande Pol & Klingelutz, 2013).

The HPV16 E7 is best known for its association with the pocket proteins retinoblastoma protein (Rb), p107 and p130 which regulate E2F transcription factors. The HPV E7 possesses conserved region 2 (CR2, residues 16 to 38), which contains the Rb-binding motif LXCXE; and conserved region 3 (CR3, residues 39 to 98), which contains two CXXC motifs that are separated by 29 or 30 residues, forming a novel zinc binding domain at its carboxy terminus (McLaughlin-Drubin & Munger, 2009), which is also present in

two copies in the primary sequence of E6. E7 is the major transforming protein of HPV (Bischof, Nacerddine, & Dejean, 2005). The carboxyl-terminal domain also contributes to E7 association with chromatin-modifying enzymes, particularly histone deacetylases and histone acetyl transferases. In particular, the E7 CR3 region contacts the C-terminal region of pRb. The E7 CR3 region also mediates inactivation of the cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitors p27 and p21 and several transcription factors that apparently contribute to HPV-mediated oncogenesis, including the TATA box-binding protein (TBP), a component of the NURD histone deacetylase complex Mi2, the acetyltransferases p300/CBP, p300/CBP-associated factor (P/CAF), and the transcription factor E2F (Avvakumov, Torchia, & Mymryk, 2003; Gordaliza, 2007; Liu, Clements, Zhao, & Marmorstein, 2006; McLaughlin-Drubin & Munger, 2009; Yim & Park, 2005).

The current study focused on dual targeting approach to find novel drug-like molecules from natural product, which provides synergistic inhibition. The natural products have been identified as promising sources of drugs for treatment and prevention of cancer in recent years (Gordaliza, 2007; Karikas, 2010; Solowey *et. al.*, 2014). A few previous studies have successfully implemented this dual targeting approach (George & Umrana, 2012).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Three dimensional structure prediction and evaluation of model

The three dimensional structure of E6 and E7 proteins were predicted using the iterative threading assembly refinement (I-TASSER) server, due to the unavailability of its biologically confirmed structure. I-TASSER is an integrated platform for automated protein structure and function prediction based on the sequence-to-structure- to-function paradigm. Starting from an amino acid sequence, I-TASSER first generates 3D atomic models from multiple threading alignments and iterative structural assembly simulations. An estimate of the accuracy of the predictions is provided based on the confidence score of the modeling (Roy, Kucukural, & Zhang, 2010).

The stereochemical property of the modelled structure of E6 and E7 was verified with the program PROCHECK. It provides a detailed check on the stereochemistry of a protein structure. The PROCHECK programs are not only useful for assessing the quality of protein structures in the process of being solved, but also of existing structures and of those being modelled on known structures (Laskowski, MacArthur, Moss, & Thornton, 1993). The energy was calculated at the atomic level using ANOLEA server. ANOLEA (Atomic Non-Local Environment Assessment) is a server that facilitates energy calculation on a protein chain, evaluating the “Non-Local Environment “of each heavy atom in the molecule. The energy for each amino acid residue of the protein chain is represented on the y-axis of the plot. Negative energy values (in green) represent favorable energy environment whereas positive values (in red) unfavorable energy environment for a given amino acid (Melo & Feytmans, 1998).

Natural product library construction and Docking study

The natural product library which contain ~ 52,000 molecules were constructed from DR. DUKE'S PHYTOCHEMICAL library [www.ars-grin.gov/duke], KNApSAcK [http://kanaya.naist.jp/KNApSAcK/] and literature search. KNApSAcK is an integrated metabolite-plant species databases which contain a three-dimensional structure of plant metabolites (Nakamura *et. al.*, 2013).

Molecular docking studies were performed using Molegro Virtual Docker (MVD). The Molegro Virtual Docker has been shown to yield a higher docking accuracy than other state-of-the-art docking products (MVD 87%, Glide 82%, Surflex 75%, FlexX 58%). It has two docking search algorithms, MolDock Optimizer and MolDock SE (Simplex Evolution). MolDock Optimizer is the default search algorithm in MVD. In order to dock the receptor and ligand, the receptor was prepared from the prepare molecule option provided. Than to search for grid, cavities were generated by using detect cavity option. And finally the ligands were provided in an sdf file format for docking using docking wizard. During docking, the following parameters were fixed: number of runs 10, population size 50, crossover rate 0.9, scaling factor 0.5, maximum iteration 2,000, and grid resolution 0.30 (Thomsen & Christensen, 2006).

Drug-Likeliness prediction

ICM molsoft was used to check the drug likeness of the screened natural products and the molecules which found to be non-toxic and having good drug like features were finalized as a putative drug. ICM molsoft can monitor important ADME-Tox and drug-likeness properties, which includes Molecular Weight (MolWeight), Number of Hydrogen Bond Acceptors (HBA), Number of Hydrogen Bond Donators (HBD), Number of Rotatable Bonds (RotB) [http://molsoft.com/mprop/].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Three dimensional structure prediction and evaluation of

The 3D structure of the HPV E6 (GI 9627104 and Accession NP_041325.1) was modeled by ab initio protein modeling tool I-TASSER as no template is available in PDB. For threading alignments and iterative structural assembly simulations of E6, the top template proteins used were 2fk4A, 2xjyA, and 2xqnT. The top model predicted by I-TASSER was considered for further steps based on the C-score (Figure 1). The C-score is a confidence score for estimating the quality of predicted models by I-TASSER. It is calculated based on the significance of threading template alignments and the convergence parameters of the structure assembly simulations. The C-score is typically in the range of [-5, 2], where a C-score of higher value signifies a model with a high confidence and vice versa.

The 3D structure of the HPV E7 (GI 9627105 and Accession NP_041326.1) also modeled by ab initio protein modeling tool I-TASSER as no template is available in PDB. For threading alignments and iterative structural

assembly simulations of E7, the top template proteins used were 2ew1A, 2f8bA, and 2b9dA. The top model predicted by I-TASSER was considered for further work based on the C-score (Figure 2).

The quality of predicted E6 and E7 structure was analyzed by PROCHECK and ANOLEA server. The PROCHECK program assessed using the Ramachandran plot. It is evident from the Ramachandran plot that the predicted E6 model has 86.9%, 11%, and 2.1% residues and predicted E7 model has 86.0%, 10.5%, and 3.5% residues in the most favorable regions, the allowed regions, and the disallowed regions, respectively. Such a percentage distribution of the protein residues determined by Ramachandran plot shows that the predicted model is of good quality. The model shows all the main chain and side chain Institute parameters to be in the “better” region. Another factor that is important for the predicted model to be reliable, is a G-factor, which is a log odds score based on the observed distribution of stereo chemical parameters. For a reliable model, the score for G-factor should be above -0.50 (Figure 3 and 4). The ANOLEA result represents the graphical view of energy values of each amino acid. It shows that most of the amino acids having negative energy values (Figure 3 and 4). The negative energy values (in green) represent favorable energy environment whereas positive values (in red) unfavorable energy environment for a given amino acid.

Molecular docking study and Drug-Likeliness prediction

Molecular docking has played key role in the identification of efficient binding of receptor and ligand. Compounds identified from docking study with most favorable binding energy were considered as hits. From the current studies, it was found that from ~52,000 natural product molecules only 127 have the complementary to the binding sites of both proteins.

From drug-likeliness prediction a few molecules identified as drug-like molecules which can block both critically essential targets of the virus. The top five molecules were tabulated in table 1. The selected natural products had a docking score ranging from -185.501 Kcal/mol to -155.775 Kcal/mol and one to eleven hydrogen bond interactions. The docking score and number of hydrogen bonds of natural products demonstrated the higher affinity with both proteins. The two dimensional structure of top five molecules and docking results shown in figure 5 and 6.

Miyakamides B1 and B2 are the new antibiotics, were isolated from the cultured broth of *Aspergillus flavus* Link var. *columnaris* FKI-0739. The structure of miyakamide B1 is N-acetyl-L-tyrosyl-N-methyl-L-phenylalanyl-(α Z)- α,β -didehydrotryptamine, and B2 is an E isomer of B1. Miyakamides shows growth inhibitory activity against brine shrimp, *Artemia salina* (Shiomi *et. al.*, 2002). Aurantiamide acetate is a selective inhibitor of Cathepsin protease (Isshiki *et. al.*, 2001). Overexpression of cathepsin D (have mitogenic activity) in aggressive cancer is observed in the breast and prostate cancer and the lysosomal protease cathepsin B, L and D, may also associate in the development and progression of malignant growth. Hence, Aurantiamide acetate may use to inhibit Cathepsin protease (Nomura & Katunuma, 2005; Zhang *et. al.*, 2015). Aurantiamide acetate was isolated first time from the plant *Piper aurantiacum* (Banerji & Ray, 1981). It also found in a

seaweed *Acanthophora spicifera* (Wahidulla, D'Souza, & Kamat, 1991; Wahidulla, D'Souza, & Kamat, 1986), *Polygonum chinensis* L (Tsai, Wang, Chang, Kuo, & Chao, 1998) and *Aspergillus penicilloides* (Isshiki et al., 2001). Proximicins were evaluated for their antitumor activity using cellular methods. Proximicin B induced apoptosis in both Hodgkin's lymphoma and T-cell leukemia cell lines and proximicin C exhibits significantly high cytotoxicity against glioblastoma and breast carcinoma cells (Brucoli *et. al.*, 2012). Also, proximicins show a weak antibacterial activity, but a strong cytostatic effect to various human tumor cell lines (Fiedler et al., 2008). The plant *Iryanthera laevis* and *Iryanthera ulei* are the rich source of Iryantherin D (Tomás-Barberán, 2001).

CONCLUSION:

Cervical cancer is the one of the leading cancers in women. Availability of the drug has brought no proper treatment for this malignancy above which it is harmful. This has occurred due to the non-specificity of the drug. The *in silico* based approach involves a series of screening steps through which the lead molecules are identified. The current study carried out to design a putative drug from natural products that can block both HPV E6 and E7 proteins concurrently. The natural products Miyakamide B1 & B2, Iryantherin D, Aurantiamide acetate, and Proximicin B were finalized as a putative drug. Though, the current study can be the best replacement for the current therapies available, these natural compounds need to be validated experimentally, and confirmed for their interaction at prognosis as well the diagnosis stage *in vitro*.

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Table 1. Docking results of top five molecules which binds with both targets HPV E6 and E7

Sr. No.	Name of the Natural Product	Source	KNAPSAc K ID	E6		E7	
				Docking energy (Kcal/mol)	No. of Hydrogen Bond	Docking energy (Kcal/mol)	No. of Hydrogen Bond
1	Miyakamide B2	Aspergillus flavus Link var. columnaris FKI-0739	C00015120	-175.862	7	-183.082	11
2	Iryantherin D	Iryanthera laevis and Iryanthera ulei	C00007975	-164.359	5	-185.501	3
3	Aurantiamide acetate	Croton hieronymi, Orthosiphon stamineus, Polygonum chinensis L, Spiraea formosana, Pierreodendron kerstingii Little, and Tribulus terrestris	C00020778	-162.055	1	-165.064	3
4	Miyakamide B1	Aspergillus flavus Link var. columnaris FKI-0739	C00015119	-159.927	6	-163.318	9
5	Proximicin B	Verrucosporo maris	C00048830	-167.054	8	-155.775	6

Figure: 1. I-TASSER predicted 3D structure of HPV E6

Figure: 2. I-TASSER predicted 3D structure of HPV E7

Plot statistics

Residues in most favoured regions [A,B,L]	126	86.9%
Residues in additional allowed regions [a,b,l,p]	15	10.3%
Residues in generously allowed regions [-a,-b,-l,-p]	1	0.7%
Residues in disallowed regions	3	2.1%
Number of non-glycine and non-proline residues	145	100.0%
Number of end-residues (excl. Gly and Pro)	2	
Number of glycine residues (shown as triangles)	4	
Number of proline residues	7	
Total number of residues	158	

Figure 3. : Procheck and ANOLEA result of HPV E6

Plot statistics

Residues in most favoured regions [A,B,L]	74	86.0%
Residues in additional allowed regions [a,b,l,p]	9	10.5%
Residues in generously allowed regions [-a,-b,-l,-p]	0	0.0%
Residues in disallowed regions	3	3.5%

Number of non-glycine and non-proline residues	86	100.0%
Number of end-residues (excl. Gly and Pro)	1	
Number of glycine residues (shown as triangles)	5	
Number of proline residues	6	

Total number of residues	98	

Figure 4. Procheck and ANOLEA result of HPV E7

Miyakamide B2
(KNAPSAcK ID: C00015120)

Iryantherin D
(KNAPSAcK ID: C00007975)

Aurantiamide acetate
(KNAPSAcK ID: C00020778)

Miyakamide B1
(KNAPSAcK ID: C00015119)

Proximicin B
(KNAPSAcK ID: C00048830)

Figure: 5. Two dimensional structure of selected top five natural products

